

Stage 1: Interview Question Guide

For Stage 1 of the semi-structured interview study reported in the paper "What You See is What You Trace - A Two-Stage Interview Study on Traceability Practices and Eye Tracking Potential"

To increase the replicability of our interview study, we noted the relevant types of codes for each question to advise other researchers on which codes we obtained from answers to each question.

As the interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner and interviewees naturally differ in the elaborateness of their answers, these questions only serve as a guide to follow for interviewers. When answers are too broad, follow-up questions are needed. On the other hand, when certain questions were already answered in previous responses, these can also be omitted.

We added short italic notes below questions whenever the quantitative or qualitative extent of the expected answer is not self-explanatory.

Introduction and Background

1. Introduction of the interviewer: briefly explain content and structure of the interview, anonymous analysis of responses and right to cancel or request data deletion at any time
2. Do you agree with this interview being recorded?
3. Please describe your role and tasks concerning software projects.
The description of the person's role should clarify how the interviewee is involved in the requirements management process of the projects they work in.

Codes: **Demographics**

4. How long (in years) have you been working in or with software projects?

Codes: **Demographics**

5. How many people work in the projects that you work on? Average, Min, Max

Codes: **Demographics**

6. How long is the runtime of projects on which you work on usually? Average, Min, Max

Codes: **Demographics**

7. Which development process is primarily used in those software projects? Agile, traditional, hybrid?
 - a. Is there a dedicated requirements elicitation or documentation phase?
 - b. If so, how long is this phase?

Codes: **Demographics**

8. How security-critical or safety-critical are the projects on which you usually work on? Are people at risk or sensitive sets of data involved?

Codes: **Demographics**

Part 1: Requirements Management (RQ1)

9. Which artifact types are used in your projects? (e.g., textual requirements, models, UML, user stories, project plan, code, tests, etc.)

The interviewer needs to pay attention that not only tools are mentioned, but the actual type of artifact.

Codes: **Artifact Types**

10. How are requirements documented in the projects on which you usually work on?

- a. Are tools being used for this documentation?
- b. Which applications are used to store and manage requirements?

When tools like a Git wiki are mentioned, a follow-up question is needed to find out what kind of information is stored in that wiki.

Codes: **Artifact Types**

Tools to manage / store Requirements

Currently linked Artifact Types

11. Is there a specific “workflow” when you are working with requirements?

This question focuses on how the different artifact types are used in the whole process and what purpose they serve.

Codes: **Artifact Types**

Tools to manage / store Requirements

Currently linked Artifact Types

12. Which document types or artifacts are often used in parallel? I.e., one is accessed directly after the other or both are shown on the screen simultaneously.

Codes: **Artifact Types**

Tools to manage / store Requirements

Currently linked Artifact Types

Part 2: Traceability Practices, Benefits and Problems (RQ2)

13. Have you heard of tracing/ traceability? Are you aware what it means?

- a. If not or unsure, give short explanation.
 - i. Software Traceability is defined as the ability to link together related artifacts from different sources within a project.
 - ii. Traceability of requirements is the ability to describe and follow the life of a requirement in both a forwards and backwards direction.
 - iii. Its advantages include requirements coverage analysis, change impact analysis or dependency analysis.

b. If yes, how was tracing implemented in your projects?

This question is one of the focal points of this interview. Let the interviewee elaborate on their own first, but make sure the following aspects are covered and ask for details when necessary. The response should describe the artifacts types that are traced, what the traces are used for and by whom.

- i. In what way? What was traced? Were there different types of links? Which granularity?
- ii. How much manual effort was required? Was it implemented for the entire project or only certain parts?
- iii. How well did it work? Were there any problems?
- iv. For what purpose did you use it?

Codes:

Artifact Types

Tools to manage / store Requirements

Familiarity with Traceability Definition

Divergence from correct Traceability Definition

Currently linked Artifact Types

Perceived Tracing Purpose

Positive Tracing Experiences

Negative Experiences

Benefit-Cost-Ratio of Tracing

14. What is your personal opinion regarding traceability? Do you think that the benefits outweigh the costs?

Codes:

Positive Tracing Experiences

Negative Experiences

Benefit-Cost-Ratio of Tracing

Part 3: Requirements for Automatic Tracing (RQ3)

15. If you pictured ideal traceability, i.e., anything could be linked with anything at no cost, which artifact types should ideally be linked in your opinion? (e.g., requirements and code, code and tests, design decisions and requirements, ...)

Codes: **Ideally linked Artifact Types**
Tool Adoption Parameters

16. Which level of granularity should trace links have? (document level, paragraph level, sentence level)

Codes: **Ideally linked Artifact Types**
Tool Adoption Parameters

17. Imagine yourself using a fully automatic approach for detecting trace links with an accuracy 100%. Which type of error do you think is worse for you? Detected links being incorrect (false positives) or correct links not being detected (false negatives)?

The answer should not only contain the type of failure that is perceived worse, but also the reasoning for this preference.

Codes: **Positive Tracing Experiences**
Worse Failure Type for Automatic Tracing
Reasoning for Failure Type Preference
Tool Adoption Parameters

Part 4: Tracing with Eye Tracking (RQ4)

18. The next questions are asked in a more open way. For that I would like you to look at this slide explaining an approach to use eye tracking to support the automatic detection of trace links. The idea is that eye tracking data are automatically recorded while people – may it be requirements engineers, architects, developers or testers – normally work on their tasks. By unintrusively recording gaze data in the background, it can be detected which artifacts are often looked at consecutively. Thereby, links are being generated between those artifacts. This way, when looking at that artifact again you can directly access related ones by following these detected links. E.g., when you look at a JIRA ticket, then at a part of a specification page and then to another related document, this gaze path could be processed to trace links between those artifacts.

19. Do you have any questions about the approach? Did you understand the concept? Did anything remain unclear?

20. Generally speaking: what do you think of the approach? Do you see a use for it? Do you have any concerns?

This question is the most important one in the interview and usually leads to a quite extensive answer. Focus on potential use cases and potential obstacles for the approach.

Codes: **General Opinion on Eye Tracking Traceability**
Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability
Concern with Eye Tracking Traceability

21. Could you see yourself having an eye tracker running while you are working or would you have concerns regarding privacy and observation? Which preconditions would need to be fulfilled for you to feel comfortable with detecting trace links based on gaze data?

Interviewees should not only state yes or no, but also why they would use an eye tracker or what would hold them back.

Codes: **Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability**
Concerns with Eye Tracking Traceability

22. Do you think that it might make sense to collect links in a context-sensitive manner? I.e., that links depend on the person's role or the task that they were working on while the trace link was collected?

Codes: **Necessity of Context-Sensitivity**

Conclusion

23. Is there anything you would like to add? Do you have any questions or remarks?

24. Would you be interested in receiving the results of the study by email?

Examples of coding process:

Adapted and translated excerpt of a response to a follow-up question to Question 9: “This concerns the whole interface descriptions, such as [...] or when new features are implemented. For those we write an individual document each, on which we work and focus.”

Applied code: **Artifact Types** – derived subcode: “**interface descriptions**”

“But if the case occurs that we take up on a previous topic, then we actually reference only the ID of the item, so that it is not repeated. Because if anything might change in this item, then we only change it in one document and due to the reference, it remains up-to-date.”

(Even though Question 9 does not refer to linked artifact types yet, interviewees occasionally already provide information on traceability practices early on. Hence, the analysis process requires a lot of awareness to also include these statements and not miss out on valuable information.)

Applied codes: **Currently linked Artifact Types** – derived subcode: “**document <-> document**”

Perceived Tracing Purpose – derived subcodes: “**prevent duplication**”, “**contribute to up-to-dateness**”

Adapted and translated excerpt of a response to Question 20: “I believe that when someone has their own little aspect of the project, currently doing nothing else but dealing with requirements, then one would have related documents that one’s gaze switches between.”

Applied code: **Benefits of Eye Tracking Traceability** – derived subcode: “**imaginable within defined requirements context**”

“But if you record someone who has their hands a little bit on everything and then gets a phone call in between, then it could be difficult. Because then he looks at his Teams chat and at an email and already forgot what he earlier wanted to do with that requirement in the first place.”

Applied code: **Concern with Eye Tracking Traceability** – derived subcode: “**difficult for people working a little bit on everything**”

The subcodes were then subsequently merged where content overlapped and overarching subcategories could be found.